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Author Correction: Time-to-event analysis mitigates the impact of symptomatic therapy on therapeutic benefit in Parkinson's disease trials

Check for updates

Gennaro Pagano , Dylan Trundell, Tanya Simuni, Nicola Pavese, Kenneth Marek, Ronald B. Postuma, Nima Shariati, Annabelle Monnet, Emma Moore, Evan W. Davies, Hanno Svoboda , Nathalie Pross, Azad Bonni, Tania Nikolcheva & for the PASADENA Investigators*, Prasinumab Study Group*

Correction to: npj Parkinson's Disease (2025) 11:193; <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41531-025-01041-9>; published online 01 July 2025

In this article the PASADENA Investigators member Jan Kassubek was incorrectly written as R. Jan Kassubek. The original article has been corrected.

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